

Ethics Requirements: Environmental Protection and Safety.

Deliverable 11.3

Submission Date: 28 January 2019

Lead Partner: ITENE

Contributor(s): All partners

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In the EU over 100 million tonnes of biowaste are thrown away each year. Currently 75% of this goes to landfill or is incinerated, causing major environmental problems biowaste produces greenhouse gases when it decomposes and contaminates soil and groundwater. Landfilling of biowaste goes against the principle of a circular economy and is a waste of nutrients, energy and resources for bioproducts. In this sense, SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate innovative solutions to transform urban biowaste into high value-added products, helping cities to increase their recycling rate and creating new circular economy business opportunities.

During SCALIBUR project, tasks that involve some risks regarding environmental hazards as well as health and safety such as the presence of hazardous substances in biowaste or even during the manipulation of the different biowaste streams, or even the generation of hazardous by-products from bioprocesses.

This deliverable describes the possible harm to the environment caused by the research and provides evidence of the commitment of partners of SCALIBUR to ensure that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed by the staff involved in this project.

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